

1 **Essential components of the lineage specification program during transition to TE in the human**
2 **embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here changes in
9 expression of Kit, LIF, and platelet derived growth factors, essential components of the lineage
10 specification program during transition to TE in the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. De Paepe, C., Cauffman, G., Verloes, A., Sterckx, J., Devroey, P., Tournaye, H., Liebaers, I. and
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